

Data management plan - Single Photon Sources for Quantum Technologies Using Nitrogen-Vacancy Centres in Diamond.

Version 1

Description

Data management plan for experimental data of a fluorescence signal from a single NV center split by a 50:50 beam-splitter registered with two photon counter detectors.

This Data Management Plan (DMP) is developed in the framework of the Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007), grant project "Single Photon Sources for Quantum Technologies Using Nitrogen-Vacancy Centres in Diamond", No. LU-BA-PA-2024/1-0071, ESS2024/465-PA-05.

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University

of Latvia" (No.
5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia, Laser Centre of the Faculty of Science and Technology of the University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Data management plan - Single Photon Sources for Quantum Technologies Using Nitrogen-Vacancy Centres in Diamond.

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Organizations:

University of Latvia

Laser Centre of the Faculty of Science and Technology of the University of Latvia

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No. 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

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3. License

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Access Rights: Public

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4. Templates

Descriptions

Single NV fluorescence photon detection data set

Time, Photon detector 1, Photon detector 2

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of this data set is to determine the number of single photons generated by a single NV center in the experimental device.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

Raw data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

N/A

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers who are working with single photons sources.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

Single photon count

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

N/A

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Notepad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

N/A

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-02-22

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2026-02-28

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Reinis Lazda (0000-0001-7169-2196)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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